

ORGANIZATIONAL FACTORS OF IMPLEMENTING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE FIELD OF COMBATING CORRUPTION

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Abstract. The article analyzes the organizational aspects of introducing artificial intelligence (AI) technologies into the activities of bodies responsible for combating corruption. The key factors influencing the effectiveness of the digital transformation of anti-corruption processes are identified, including institutional, legal and regulatory, human resource, and infrastructural prerequisites. Special attention is paid to the need to form a comprehensive organizational system for managing digital innovations in the public sector. Based on an analysis of international and national experience, proposals and recommendations are developed to improve the organizational model for implementing artificial intelligence in anti-corruption activities.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, combating corruption, organizational factors, digital transformation, public administration, anti-corruption policy.

Modern trends in the digitalization of public administration are shaping new approaches to combating corruption. Artificial intelligence is becoming an important tool for analyzing large volumes of data, forecasting corruption risks, and automating control and inspection functions. However, the effectiveness of its application depends not only on the level of technological development but also directly on the quality of organizational support. Insufficient interagency cooperation, a lack of necessary competencies, and the absence of a unified information infrastructure create serious obstacles to the implementation of digital innovations.

In both academic and practical environments, it is increasingly emphasized that the successful use of artificial intelligence in the anti-corruption sphere is possible only with systematic organizational support. The purpose of this article is to identify the main organizational factors influencing the introduction of artificial intelligence into anti-corruption mechanisms and to develop ways to improve them.

Experience in using artificial intelligence in the public and corporate sectors demonstrates a high degree of compatibility between software algorithms and technological approaches applied in building analytical systems aimed at identifying corruption risks. This is confirmed by the possibility of universal use of the same software solutions across different sectors [1]. Based on the most significant examples of international practice, the article highlights the key organizational factors that must be taken into account when using artificial intelligence to combat corruption in the public sector.

The experience of China, particularly the “Zero Trust” system, is of special interest. This project represented a large-scale experiment in the use of artificial intelligence to detect corruption cases in the public sector [2]. Despite the high efficiency achieved in identifying

suspicious cases, the relative lack of transparency in the decision-making algorithms complicated their subsequent verification and legal assessment by law enforcement agencies. As a result, additional human and material resources were required to operate the system, and some identified cases did not receive legally significant confirmation [3]. Within the framework of the “Zero Trust” project, the analytical capacity of artificial intelligence was clearly shown to exceed the capabilities of the supporting law enforcement infrastructure.

The experience of Brazil is also noteworthy. Under Operation “Serenata do Amor,” an artificial intelligence system named Rosie was developed to identify violations, including corruption-related offenses, in the reimbursement of expenses incurred by members of parliament in the course of their official activities [4]. The Rosie algorithm [5] analyzes data from official registries and open sources to identify unjustified or disproportionate expenses. Confirmed cases are forwarded to authorized supervisory bodies and published on the Jarbas platform [6] as well as on social media. This experience demonstrates the effectiveness of narrowly specialized, practice-oriented solutions, integration with electronic document management systems, and transparency as an important element of the organizational model.

In Mexico, a corruption risk index was developed in the field of public procurement [7]. This system made it possible to identify partial monopolization of the public contracts market, potential collusion among companies, and corruption risks involving public officials. As a result, a ranking of the corruption risk level of procurement participants was formed. However, the main drawback of this approach lies in the limited direct applicability of the results in the operational activities of law enforcement agencies, as the findings were largely generalized in nature.

The use of artificial intelligence during the COVID-19 pandemic is also of particular importance. The pandemic led to an increase in legal and corruption risks, which were analyzed in detail using the example of Russia [8]. Under conditions of a sharp increase in the volume of public procurement, many states turned to AI-based anti-corruption solutions. In particular, the Open Contracting Partnership [9] promoted the introduction of unified standards for transparency in public contracts. According to data from the Office of the Comptroller General of Colombia, in 2024 the use of artificial intelligence at the OCEANO center led to the review of nearly 19 percent of contracts concluded during the pandemic period [10]. This experience confirms that clearly defined and realistic objectives significantly enhance the effectiveness of artificial intelligence.

Within the system of public administration, artificial intelligence can be understood as a set of technologies aimed at processing big data, modeling the behavior of actors, and making decisions with minimal human involvement. In the field of combating corruption, artificial intelligence is used to:

- automatically identify suspicious transactions and conflicts of interest;
- analyze declarations of income and expenses of public officials;
- forecast corruption risks in public procurement;
- monitor official activities and citizens’ appeals.

The readiness of the public administration system to implement artificial intelligence is determined by a number of interrelated factors, including institutional structure, the legal and regulatory framework, human resource capacity, and information infrastructure.

Thus, organizational support serves as a connecting element between the technological potential of artificial intelligence and its practical application in anti-corruption activities. International experience shows that the success of digital anti-corruption initiatives largely depends on interagency cooperation and a systematic approach to innovation management.

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